

Chapter 5

Supplementary Material

Linking the functional traits of Australian *Acacia* species to their geographic distribution and invasion status

Martín-Forés I.¹, Andrew S.C.², Guerin G.R.¹, and Gallagher R.V.³

¹School of Biological Sciences, The University of Adelaide, Adelaide 5005, South Australia, Australia

²CSIRO Land and Water, Canberra, Australian Capital Territory, Australia

³Hawkesbury Institute for the Environment, Western Sydney University, Richmond 2753, New South Wales, Australia

Table 5.S1. Kruskal-Wallis χ^2 values, mean and standard error of area of occupancy (AOO; km²), extent of occurrence (EOO; km²), and climatic niche breadths (MAT: mean annual temperature, MaxT: maximum temperature of the warmest month, MAP: mean annual precipitation, PDM: precipitation of the driest month, aridity: aridity index calculated as the quotient between annual precipitation and potential evapotranspiration) for the different levels of invasion status. Different letters in the same line indicate significant differences among invasion status from Kruskal-Wallis tests based on Dunn's non-parametric all-pairs comparison test and adjusted p-values with Holm's correction. Significance levels ($. \leq 0.1$; $* \leq 0.05$; $** \leq 0.01$; $*** \leq 0.001$).

Variable	χ^2	Non-introduced (629 species)	Casual (317 species)	Naturalized (55 species)	Invasive (24 species)
AOO	261.23***	212.4 ± 14.0 ^a	640.8 ± 42.2 ^b	1152 ± 199.1 ^c	1660 ± 244.1 ^c
EOO	275.19***	234658.5 ± 22229.8 ^a	920467.1 ± 66519.0 ^b	1490266 ± 201997.7 ^c	3421045 ± 382083.4 ^c
MAT	205.27***	2.93 ± 0.08 ^a	4.71 ± 0.12 ^b	6.01 ± 0.33 ^c	7.25 ± 0.49 ^c
MaxT	169.67***	4.49 ± 0.11 ^a	6.48 ± 0.16 ^b	8.10 ± 0.36 ^c	9.98 ± 0.51 ^c
MAP	185.72***	288.6 ± 12.0 ^a	544.3 ± 24.4 ^b	621.8 ± 49.3 ^c	1106.2 ± 140.6 ^d
PDM	187.78***	9.23 ± 0.39 ^a	17.86 ± 0.87 ^b	28.62 ± 2.20 ^c	51.67 ± 4.78 ^d
Aridity	189.3***	0.18 ± 0.01 ^a	0.34 ± 0.02 ^b	0.42 ± 0.03 ^c	0.74 ± 0.07 ^d

Table 5.S2. Kruskal-Wallis χ^2 values, mean and standard error of the three traits considered (maximum plant height, seed dry mass and specific leaf area – SLA) for the different levels of invasion status. Notice that the values are log transformed. Different letters in the same line indicate significant differences among invasion status from Kruskal-Wallis tests based on Dunn’s non-parametric all-pairs comparison test and adjusted p-values with Holm’s correction. Significance levels ($. \leq 0.1$; $* \leq 0.05$; $** \leq 0.01$; $*** \leq 0.001$).

Trait	χ^2	Not-introduced	Casual	Naturalized	Invasive
Max plant height (m)	255.3***	0.69 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.61 \pm 0.05 ^b	1.73 \pm 0.09 ^b	2.53 \pm 0.15 ^c
Seed dry mass (g)	74.6***	2.31 \pm 0.03 ^a	2.75 \pm 0.04 ^b	2.77 \pm 0.11 ^b	2.85 \pm 0.12 ^b
SLA (mm²/mg)	61.2***	1.51 \pm 0.01 ^a	1.59 \pm 0.02 ^b	1.78 \pm 0.06 ^c	1.99 \pm 0.10 ^c